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GCT: A Granger-Causal Transformer for Multivariate Traffic Analysis in Smart Villages

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Predicting vehicle traffic optimizes transportation management and urban planning. In this article, we combine real-time data from vehicle-detection Internet of Things (IoT) devices with external variables from Google Trends. Integrating such heterogeneous, complex data streams is challenging for traditional machine learning models that struggle to capture the dynamics of traffic patterns, which are influenced by multiple interdependent factors. To effectively model these complex, interdependent factors, we introduce the Granger-Causal Transformer (GCT), a transformer-based architecture for traffic prediction that integrates an LSTM network with a modified multi-head attention mechanism. This mechanism extends Granger causality to the spatio-temporal domain to analyze all causality relations between features consistently, while capturing long-range dependencies and temporal patterns. Before applying GCT, we generate lagged versions of the Google Trends time series to capture lead and lag effects. Tourists usually make searches about their destination weeks before traveling, so peaks in search interest occur earlier than peaks in weekly traffic volume. Using lags aligns the predictors with weekly traffic volume and allows the model to use past searches to predict future traffic. We semantically validate the Google Trends terms by comparing each term with a reference string describing the study area, using a language model aligned with the data's linguistic context. We then apply a dual filtering process comprising Granger noncausality and correlation tests to minimize noise and redundancy. We evaluate our proposed methodology against classical statistical models, deep learning models, large foundation models, and transformers across two case studies. The results demonstrate consistently superior performance and generalizability, with GCT achieving R^2 improvements between 47% and 68% compared to the best-performing baselines across both settings, alongside substantial reductions in MAE and MSE.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning algorithms**; *Neural networks*; Artificial intelligence; • **Networks** → *Network architectures*;

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1 Introduction

Time series analysis plays an important role in the **Internet of Things (IoT)** domain, contributing to various fields such as healthcare [2, 23, 35], industry [4, 18, 49], and transportation [12, 65, 70]. Recent advancements in **Large Language Models (LLMs)** have opened new opportunities to enhance time series methodologies across these domains. LLM-inspired architectures emphasize dependency modeling and multivariate sequence processing, transforming tasks such as behavior prediction, anomaly detection, and real-time decision-making. Specifically, in transportation, LLM-based approaches can advance traffic forecasting by leveraging historical data to build more robust predictive models, improving traffic management strategies and infrastructure planning [38].

Advances in traffic prediction have used a range of **Machine Learning (ML)** techniques for multivariate time series data. Initially, statistical models like **AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)** were preferred because they capture temporal dependencies in a linear manner [34, 55]. However, as traffic patterns became more complex and the volume of data increased, deep learning models such as **Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)**, **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)**, and **Gated Recurrent Units (GRU)** became widely used [28, 31, 41]. These models can capture complex nonlinear relationships and time-based dependencies that ARIMA cannot efficiently handle. Recently, transformer-based architectures have gained popularity due to their ability to manage long-term dependencies through attention mechanisms [9, 52, 69]. Advancements in LLMs, which are built upon transformer architectures, have demonstrated their effectiveness in handling sequential data, which can enhance methodologies in time series analysis, including in applications such as traffic forecasting [52, 69].

With the move towards sustainable tourism, especially in rural regions, demand forecasting and optimized resource allocation require real-time as well as historical and fine-grained data about the local conditions. Though IoT devices are a primary source of data, complexities associated with installation ease (due to local geography), device maintenance, data storage, and communication, mean that secondary data sources can serve to augment spatio-temporal data about rural regions. Social data, particularly Google Trends, have emerged as a promising additional data source that can mitigate reporting delays and data incompleteness, providing real-time insights to predict future trends [14]. Incorporating Google Trends data into mixed-data sampling models has been shown to significantly enhance forecast accuracy [6], and it is widely used to predict tourism traffic demand [45, 64]. However, Google Trends data may be lagged relative to other sources; for example, a tourist might search for a destination a few weeks or even months before traveling. This anticipatory search behavior introduces an additional challenge in aligning the timing of these search metrics with actual travel events.

A key aspect of **Neural Network (NN)** modeling is understanding that not all input variables contribute equally to the forecasting task. To address this, studies have introduced techniques into ML models to evaluate and prioritize the importance of variables. Tank et al. [59] proposed **Component-Wise Multilayer Perceptron (cMLP)** and **Component-Wise LSTM (cLSTM)**, which incorporate causality into deep learning models to automatically select and prioritize input

series with significant causal influence on the output series. Others, such as [62], introduce **Causal Attention Mechanism (CATT)**, a framework that uses causal inference to remove spurious correlations by separating valid (causal) features from invalid (non-causal) features. Similarly, CausalFormer [32] introduced a transformer-based model architecture that integrates causality with attention by applying causal convolutions before the attention mechanism and using penalties to identify and prioritize causal input series, without relying on statistical tests for causal validation.

Approaches such as CATT and CausalFormer introduce causal structures by modifying attention mechanisms to emphasize or isolate features that are causal based on observed patterns. While these strategies help mitigate spurious correlations, the resulting causal inferences are driven primarily by architectural heuristics rather than by statistical verification. Consequently, there remains an opportunity for methods that systematically integrate and validate causal relationships within the attention framework through formal empirical tests.

This gap motivates the development of our **Granger-Causal Transformer (GCT)**, an architecture designed to explicitly incorporate Granger causality into the attention mechanism to statistically test and model causal dependencies between pairs of variables or inputs. Granger causality represents the causality between two time series as a regression task, with a “Granger” cause determined if one time series can successfully predict another. Here, Granger causality is used as a forecasting criterion: past values of a variable X improve predictions of another variable Y when we condition on the lagged values of Y . This does not imply structural or true causation [25]. GCT combines an LSTM layer with a modified multi-head attention mechanism. The LSTM layer captures sequential dependencies, while the attention layer integrates a causality mask, which accounts for Granger-causal relationships between variables, ensuring that the model captures both temporal dependencies and causal interactions while also reflecting the strength and precedence of relationships between variables. Prior to GCT prediction, we validate the external variables using a **Language Model (LM)** aligned with the data’s linguistic context and then apply a Granger causality test as a feature selection filter, combined with a correlation filter. This dual-filtering approach ensures that only causally relevant and highly correlated time series are selected and subsequently passed to the GCT architecture for prediction. Additionally, we conduct an ablation test to evaluate the contribution and significance of each element of our methodology.

We validate the methodology in two case studies. In the first study (Alpujarra, southern Spain), we forecast weekly vehicle counts for the three-village area (Pampaneira, Bubión, and Capileira) connected by a single access road. In the second study (Salt Lake City, USA), we aggregate weekly counts from four stations positioned along the main roads leading into the city (from North, South, East, and West). In both cases, we forecast several weeks in advance, as tourists typically plan their trips well in advance. The predictions are made at the destination-wide level rather than for specific roads or locations, as tourists usually visit multiple places within the area.

The main contributions of this work are highlighted as follows:

- We present GCT, a transformer-based architecture that modifies the attention mechanism to adjust attention weights based on causality between series. In particular, we incorporate a mask that introduces the Granger causality test into the attention mechanism.
- We introduce a feature validation step using a LM as a validator, ensuring that only semantically relevant features are retained for a subsequent dual statistical filtering process, which applies both a Granger causality test and a correlation filter to refine the selection of lagged features for time series prediction.

- We conduct an ablation study to evaluate our method by exploring how the inclusion or exclusion of the causality mask in the transformer and the two feature selection mechanisms—causality and correlation filtering—affect model performance. This analysis helps assess the contribution of each component to the overall prediction metrics.
- We validate the robustness and generalizability of our GCT pipeline across two distinct contexts: a rural setting with Spanish-language data and an urban setting with English-language data, demonstrating its effectiveness in different environments.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the related work. Section 3 discusses the theoretical foundations of Granger causality and the transformer attention mechanism. Section 4 presents our methodology. Section 5 outlines the initial case study. Section 6 presents the experimental results, including the ablation study (Section 6.3) and a second case study to validate generalizability (Section 6.4). This section also discusses the findings (Section 6.5) and details limitations and future work (Section 6.6). Finally, Section 7 concludes the article.

2 Related Work

Classical statistical models like ARIMA [34, 55] and its multivariate variant ARIMAX [58] are widely utilized for predicting traffic flow and analyzing time series data in public transportation systems. ARIMAX has proven more effective than ARIMA by incorporating external factors, as shown in studies focusing on travel times [44] and accident predictions [30]. This concept of using exogenous data has been extended to sources like social media, where Twitter activity and sentiment from the previous night have been used to predict the next morning’s commute traffic [66]. With advancements in deep learning, models that capture complex traffic patterns have emerged. RNNs, particularly LSTM and GRU, have enhanced traffic flow prediction by modeling temporal dependencies [31, 43, 57]. Architectural refinements, such as using stacked bidirectional LSTMs, have been proposed to capture both forward and backward temporal dependencies more effectively, even addressing missing data issues [16]. Additionally, combining convolutional layers (e.g., Conv1D) with LSTMs has improved the ability to capture spatial-temporal patterns [42], a concept also extended to architectures utilizing GRU-based layers [27]. Recently, transformer-based models have gained importance for their capability to handle large-scale datasets and capture long-range dependencies, as evidenced by their application in spatio-temporal traffic prediction [60] and traffic congestion forecasting [48].

Several studies have incorporated causality to determine the importance of variables in multivariate models. For instance, Long et al. [42] improve traffic prediction models by utilizing causality to identify the most influential variables within NNs. Other researchers have combined causality with ML models to enhance prediction performance. One approach to this combination is through regularization penalties. For example, Tank et al. [59] introduce the cMLP and cLSTM, NN architectures designed for Granger causality detection in multivariate temporal series. cMLP employs separate multilayer perceptrons for each target series, applying group lasso, sparse group lasso, or hierarchical lasso penalties to the input weights. This penalization helps identify causal relationships between the input series and the output series and also enables automatic lag selection. Similarly, cLSTM utilizes individual LSTM networks for each output series, with group lasso penalties imposed on the input weights to determine causal influences. Causality between time series is then determined by the presence of non-zero weights connecting the input series to the output within these networks.

Rather than relying on sparsity-inducing penalties, other researchers have explored incorporating causality directly into model architectures [32] or through explicit causal inference mechanisms

[62], such as encoding causal relationships within transformer architectures themselves. For instance, Wang and Zhou [62] reinterpret the role of attention mechanisms in transformers from a causality perspective, concentrating specifically on image data and not adapting their approach to domains such as time-series forecasting. They introduce the concept of confounders, which are variables that influence both the input data and the attention mechanism, leading to spurious correlations that can negatively impact model performance. To address confounding without regularization penalties, they propose a causal inference framework that removes the influence of confounders by applying interventions based on the do-operation and front-door criterion, enabling the attention mechanism to focus on truly causal relationships rather than spurious correlations. Taking a different architectural approach, Kong et al. [32] introduce CausalFormer, a transformer architecture used for temporal causal discovery in time series data. CausalFormer employs multi-kernel causal convolution blocks to learn causal representations by convolving each time series with causal kernels under temporal priority constraints. After training the transformer, they apply **Regression Relevance Propagation (RRP)** as a *post hoc* interpretability method to decompose the model's predictions into relevance scores. This post-attention analysis enables the extraction and construction of meaningful causal relationships from the trained model.

Recent popular examples that utilize transformers include large foundation models for time series, pre-trained on web-scale data and used in zero-shot settings. These models vary in their design and accessibility. Some, such as Lag-Llama [50] and Chronos [3], are designed for probabilistic forecasting, outputting predictive distributions rather than single-point forecasts. Other models, such as TimeGPT [24], are primarily accessible via proprietary APIs. In contrast, publicly available models, such as TimesFM [17] and Moirai [63], focus on deterministic point forecasting. Among these, TimesFM is a decoder-only transformer, pre-trained primarily on Google Trends and Wikipedia page views, which aligns well with demand and seasonality patterns. It produces strong zero-shot forecasts. Because it does not take exogenous time series at forecast time, external effects are captured only indirectly through recurring patterns learned during pre-training and visible in the series history. Another large foundational model is Moirai, which is a unified transformer trained on diverse time series corpora; it supports multivariate inputs and exogenous covariates at inference, enables multi-horizon forecasting, and can operate in zero-shot mode using official checkpoints. Both provide competitive baselines, though neither explicitly encodes statistical causality nor structured lag selection within attention.

Regarding feature selection prior to the architecture, various approaches are employed. For example, Li et al. [37] use the Pearson Correlation Coefficient in a **Broad Learning System (BLS)** to enhance prediction accuracy by filtering highly correlated features, while Salman et al. [54] employ Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient to improve feature selection stability in high-dimensional datasets, using methods like the arithmetic mean and L2 norm. In contrast, some authors have leveraged causality for feature selection [67]. Long et al. [42] utilize causal relationships to select features prior to their hybrid model combining 1D convolutional NNs and LSTM networks. In a similar way, Fafoutellis and Vlahogianni [22] apply a Granger causality test to select a reduced, causally informed input space for a multitask LSTM. Yu et al. [40] introduce the **Fair Causal Feature Selection Algorithm (FairCFS)**, an approach that accounts for causal relationships to ensure fairness in classification tasks.

Considering the absence of methods that directly incorporate Granger causality into the attention mechanism of transformer models and the lack of approaches that combine both correlation and causality-based feature selection within such architectures, we propose our methodology to include these components.

3 Background

3.1 Granger Causality Test

The Granger Causality test [25] is a statistical method used to determine if one time series can predict another. The main idea is that if a time series X Granger-causes another time series Y , it means that changes in X happen first and are reflected later in Y , implying there is a delay between the two. In this case, past values of X provide information that helps predict Y beyond the information in the past values of Y alone [46].

Consider two time series, X_t and Y_t . The autoregressive models used in the Granger causality test are the Restricted Model (without X) and the Full Model (with X). The Restricted Model, which uses past values of Y to predict Y , is defined as follows:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t. \quad (1)$$

The Full Model, which uses past values of Y and X to predict Y , is defined as follows:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \beta_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_p Y_{t-p} + \gamma_1 X_{t-1} + \gamma_2 X_{t-2} + \dots + \gamma_p X_{t-p} + \nu_t. \quad (2)$$

The null hypothesis of the Granger causality test is that X_t does not Granger-cause Y_t , meaning that all the coefficients γ_j are equal to zero. This hypothesis is tested using an F-test, which compares the **Sum of Squared Residuals (SSRs)** from the restricted and unrestricted models:

$$F = \frac{(SSR_{\text{restricted}} - SSR_{\text{full}})/p}{SSR_{\text{full}}/(n - 2p - 1)}, \quad (3)$$

where

- $SSR_{\text{restricted}}$ is the SSRs of the model without X .
- SSR_{full} is the SSRs of the model with X .
- p is the number of lags (number of previous periods used to predict the current value).
- n is the number of observations.

The F-test statistic calculated above follows a specific probability distribution known as the F-distribution, which depends on the number of lags and the number of observations. To make a decision, we compare the calculated F-test value to a critical value obtained from the F-distribution table at a chosen significance level of 5%, a commonly used threshold in statistical hypothesis testing to assess result significance [10]. If the F-test value is greater than the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that X_t Granger-causes Y_t . This means that X_t contains useful information for predicting Y_t that is not already captured by the past values of Y_t alone.

3.2 Transformer: Attention Mechanism

Transformers are NN architectures designed to leverage parallel processing and effectively capture long-range dependencies within data [61]. Central to their design is the attention mechanism, which allows the model to dynamically focus on the most relevant parts of the input sequence when generating each element of the output, enabling it to model contextual relationships across the sequence. A fundamental component of the attention mechanism is self-attention, where the input sequence itself serves as the queries, keys, and values. Given an input sequence $X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, where x_i is the feature vector for the i th element, the self-attention mechanism is computed as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V. \quad (4)$$

In this formulation, the input X is linearly transformed into three distinct matrices: queries (Q), keys (K), and values (V). These are computed as:

$$Q = XW_Q, \quad K = XW_K, \quad V = XW_V, \quad (5)$$

where W_Q , W_K , and W_V are learnable weight matrices. The dot product of the queries and keys, QK^T , results in attention scores that are scaled by $\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_k}}$, where d_k is the dimension of the keys, to avoid excessively large values. In a multivariate NN applied to time series data, the matrix $\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ represents pairwise similarities between different time steps in these input series, rather than only similarities across series. Each element in this matrix corresponds to the similarity between the query from one timestep and the key from another timestep, allowing the model to capture relationships between the inputs and adjust the attention scores accordingly [39]. The softmax function is then applied to normalize these scores, ensuring they sum to 1. The resulting weights are then used to compute a weighted sum of the values (V), producing the final output of the self-attention mechanism. In the multi-head attention mechanism, the process of self-attention is repeated multiple times in parallel. Instead of computing a single set of attention scores, the input is projected into several different subspaces, producing multiple sets of queries, keys, and values (Q_i, K_i, V_i) for each head i .

4 Methodology

Our methodology (see Figure 1) begins with the validation of input series using an LM aligned with the data's linguistic context, followed by the generation of lagged versions of the time series, which are filtered to retain only those series that exhibit significant causal relationships and correlations, as detailed in Section 4.1 and step 1 of Algorithm 1. The filtered features are then normalized and passed to our architecture to generate predictions. Our architecture consists of an LSTM layer to capture temporal dependencies (see Section 4.2 and step 2 of Algorithm 1) and a multi-head attention layer with a causality mask to integrate causal relationships (see Section 4.3 and step 3 of Algorithm 1). Additionally, the model includes a normalization layer to stabilize learning, residual connections to facilitate gradient flow and prevent vanishing gradients [68], and dense layers with dropout to learn abstract representations and reduce overfitting [56]. This methodology provides a structured temporal and causality-aware approach for multivariate time-series forecasting. Finally, Section 4.4 details the training process, hyperparameters, and the cross-validation strategy used for evaluation.

4.1 Feature Selection

We use external social data from search engines commonly used by visitors to plan their trips. Specifically, for our use cases, we use Google Trends, which provides data on how often a given term was searched on Google each week.¹ In Google Search, a higher volume of a term within a week raises the relative search-interest index reported by Google Trends. We treat these indices as leading indicators. People typically search for destinations and activities before visiting. Hence, sustained increases in search interest are expected to precede subsequent tourist inflows. Importantly, these searches typically occur pre-trip from the tourists' regions of origin, where internet access is generally widespread, mitigating concerns about low internet penetration within the destination itself. To obtain external series for a destination (study area), we begin with an initial set of social data terms, for example, in our use case, Google Trends terms that represent the local context and then expand them with terms frequently searched for in the same region and topic.

¹<https://trends.google.com/trends/>.

Fig. 1. Methodology.

Then, we establish semantic relationships to ensure that only semantically relevant time series are considered. Because aligning the LM with the linguistic and contextual domain of the data is important for semantic validation, our methodology adapts this step based on the Google Trends terms' language. For example, in our first case study (Section 5), which uses Spanish queries, we use BETO, a pre-trained Spanish LM² [11]. BETO follows the BERT-Base architecture and applies the **Whole Word Masking (WWM)** technique for improved token representations [19]. The model was trained on a large Spanish corpus, using a vocabulary of approximately 31,000 subword units generated with the SentencePiece algorithm [33], and optimized over 2 million training steps. BETO generates dense vector embeddings that effectively capture both semantic and syntactic relationships between terms. In contrast, for our English-language generalizability study (Section 6.4), we use the BERT model³ to ensure proper alignment.

Using the selected LM, we encode a reference string that describes the study area and each candidate term (query terms in the search engine). We then compute cosine similarity (see Equation (6)) between the reference string embedding and each term embedding and retain only terms with similarity $\geq \tau$. By applying a cosine similarity threshold to discriminate relevant semantic relationships [51], we filter out semantically unrelated terms and retain only the most pertinent ones. Next, for those Google Trends terms, we obtain their associated weekly time series that represents the number of times each term was searched in Google. This yields a semantically aligned set of terms whose weekly numeric values serve as the external time series:

$$\text{cosine_similarity}(A, B) = \frac{A \cdot B}{|A||B|}. \quad (6)$$

After that, we account for temporal dependencies and incorporate historical information by generating lagged versions of each series. This allows the model to consider past values when making predictions, enhancing its ability to capture dynamic relationships within the data. Furthermore, incorporating irrelevant time series can lead to overfitting, increased computational complexity, and

²<https://huggingface.co/dccuchile/bert-base-spanish-wwm-uncased>.

³<https://huggingface.co/bert-base-uncased>.

Algorithm 1: GCT Training and Inference

Require: Y : Target Variable, $X = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n\}$: Predictor Variables, p : Number of lags
Ensure: \hat{Y} : Predicted Target Variable

- 1: $X_{LM} \leftarrow \{x_i \in X \mid \text{cosine_similarity}(\text{LM}(x_i), \text{LM}(\text{reference_string})) \geq \text{threshold}\}$
- 2: $Z \leftarrow [Y; X_{LM}]$
- 3: $Z_{\text{norm}} \leftarrow \text{Normalize}(Z)$
- 4: **Step 1:** Feature Selection: Causality and Correlation
- 5: **for** $i \leftarrow 1$ **to** n **do**
- 6: **for** $j \leftarrow 1$ **to** p **do**
- 7: Generate lagged series: $X_{i,t-j}$
- 8: Retain $X_{i,t-j}$ if it satisfies causality and correlation thresholds
- 9: **end for**
- 10: **end for**
- 11: **Step 2:** LSTM Component
- 12: $H_{\text{LSTM}} \leftarrow \text{LSTM}(Z_{\text{norm}})$ ▷ Extract temporal dependencies
- 13: $H_{\text{norm}} \leftarrow \text{LayerNorm}(H_{\text{LSTM}})$
- 14: **Step 3:** GCT Architecture
- 15: Initialize causality matrix: $C \leftarrow \mathbf{0}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$
- 16: **for** $i \leftarrow 1$ **to** $n+1$ **do** ▷ Y is included as X_{n+1}
- 17: **for** $j \leftarrow 1$ **to** $n+1$ **do**
- 18: $C_{ij} \leftarrow \frac{1}{\text{best_lag}(X_i, X_j)} \cdot \mathbb{I}(X_i \rightarrow X_j)$
- 19: **end for**
- 20: **end for**
- 21: $Q \leftarrow H_{\text{norm}} W_Q, K \leftarrow H_{\text{norm}} W_K, V \leftarrow H_{\text{norm}} W_V$
- 22: $\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) \leftarrow \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \odot (1 + C)\right)V$
- 23: $H_{\text{attention}} \leftarrow \text{Attention}(Q, K, V)$
- 24: Add residual connection: $H_{\text{residual}} \leftarrow H_{\text{norm}} + H_{\text{attention}}$
- 25: Concatenate outputs: $H_{\text{concat}} \leftarrow \text{Concat}(H_{\text{residual}}, H_{\text{norm}})$
- 26: $H_{\text{FFN}} \leftarrow \text{FeedForwardBlock}(H_{\text{concat}})$ ▷ Dense + Dropout layers
- 27: $\hat{Y} \leftarrow \text{Dense}(H_{\text{FFN}}, \text{units} = 1)$
- return** \hat{Y}

diminished forecasting performance [29]. To address these challenges, we apply causal relationship filtering and correlation-based filtering during pre-processing.

The next step involves creating lagged versions of the social data. This step ensures that the model accounts for historical values that may influence the target variable Y over different time periods. From the generated series, we select those that have a significant relevance.

Let $\{X_t\}$ denote a time series. The lagged versions of this series are represented as $X_{t-1}, X_{t-2}, \dots, X_{t-p}$, where p is the maximum lag considered. Specifically, we select the series where the p-value of the Granger test satisfies $p \leq 0.05$ [10], indicating that they contribute valuable predictive information. The selection process described in step 1 of Algorithm 1 can be summarized as follows:

$$\text{Select } X_{t-i} \text{ such that } p\text{-value of Granger test}(X_{t-i} \rightarrow Y) \leq 0.05. \quad (7)$$

Since including all the series and their respective lags may introduce redundancy and noise, we select only the most relevant ones based on their correlation. Only series with a correlation coefficient greater than a predefined threshold, α , are retained:

$$|\text{Corr}(X_{t-i}, Y_t)| > \alpha. \quad (8)$$

Here, $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a threshold applied to the absolute Pearson correlation between each lagged candidate time series and the target. Lower α makes the filter less restrictive and retains more predictors, increasing the risk of redundancy and overfitting, whereas higher α retains fewer, more strongly correlated time series, at the risk of discarding informative signals.

This filtering guarantees that the retained time series not only have a causal impact on Y but also exhibit a strong linear relationship with it. By enforcing both causality and correlation, we ensure that the model incorporates only those predictors that provide relevant predictive information while reducing complexity by eliminating less relevant series. In our methodology, these Granger and correlation screens serve only as a filtering step for the lagged social time series. The retained signals are then modeled by the non-linear architecture (see Section 4.3), which captures both linear and non-linear interactions. Unlike penalty-based approaches such as Lasso, our filter-based method separates variable screening from model training. This avoids penalty hyperparameter tuning, improves transparency, and allows the transformer to focus on capturing complex interactions among the validated causal predictors through the attention mask.

4.2 LSTM Component

The first layer of our architecture is an LSTM layer, which functions as a sequential encoder. LSTMs are designed to process information sequentially, which makes them well-suited for capturing local temporal dependencies and sequential order [53]. Its role is to first process the input features, injecting a temporal inductive bias and transforming the sequence of inputs into a sequence of enriched, context-aware hidden state vectors. This denoises the inputs and highlights relevant temporal patterns. This feature extraction provides the subsequent GCT layer with a cleaner, contextually richer input.

This component involves two sequential operations. First, the input features are passed through an LSTM layer, which is configured with recurrent units to produce a sequence of vectors known as hidden states that encode and summarize the learned temporal dependencies. Second, this sequence of hidden states is processed by a Layer Normalization operation. The purpose of this normalization step is to stabilize the distribution of the hidden state activations. This is an important step to mitigate potential vanishing or exploding gradient issues and ensure that the inputs fed to the subsequent GCT layer are well-scaled, which facilitates a more stable and efficient training process [5].

4.3 GCT

GCT incorporates an attention mechanism that accounts for Granger-causal relationships between time series in a transformer. To that end, we construct a causality matrix C which serves as a mask. This mask is applied to the attention mechanism to adjust the attention similarity weight matrix. Figure 2 shows both the regular transformer and the proposed attention mechanism with the causality mask, which is formulated as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \odot (1 + C)\right)V. \quad (9)$$

We construct the matrix C by evaluating pairwise Granger causality between time series i and j , where:

$$C_{ij} = \frac{1}{\text{best_lag}(i, j)} \cdot \mathbb{I}(X_i \rightarrow X_j). \quad (10)$$

Here, the indicator function $\mathbb{I}(X_i \rightarrow X_j)$ equals 1 if series X_i Granger-causes series X_j , and 0 otherwise. If series i does not Granger-cause series j , then $C_{ij} = 0$, meaning no adjustment is made to the attention score for this pair. However, if series i significantly Granger-causes series j , the corresponding entry C_{ij} is set to $\frac{1}{\text{best_lag}(i, j)}$, where $\text{best_lag}(i, j)$ is an integer in $\{1, \dots, p_{\max}\}$, representing the shortest significant time delay found between the two series. p_{\max} represents the maximum viable lag, beyond which the relationship between the time series becomes too weak or

Fig. 2. Comparison of attention mechanisms. The left image shows the original attention mechanism, while the right image shows the attention mechanism with causality mask.

Table 1. GCT Architecture

Layer No	Type	Shape	Parameters
0	Input	$(N_{Batch}, \text{num_variables})$	$N_{Batch} = 64$
1	LSTM	$(N_{Batch}, \text{lstm_units})$	$\text{lstm_units} = 32$
2	LayerNormalization	$(N_{Batch}, \text{lstm_units})$	-
3	Multi-HeadAttention with Causality Mask	$(N_{Batch}, \text{num_variables})$	$\text{num_heads} = 4, \text{key_dim} = \text{num_variables}$
4	Add	$(N_{Batch}, \text{num_variables})$	-
5	Concatenate	$(N_{Batch}, \text{lstm_units} + \text{num_variables})$	-
6	Dense	$(N_{Batch}, \text{dense_units})$	$\text{dense_units} = 64$
7	Dropout	$(N_{Batch}, \text{dense_units})$	$\text{dropout} = 0.15$
8	Dense	$(N_{Batch}, \text{dense_units}/2)$	-
9	Dropout	$(N_{Batch}, \text{dense_units}/2)$	-
10	Dense	$(N_{Batch}, 1)$	-

noisy to be informative. For example, in our use cases, we set $p_{max} = 12$, based on previous literature that states that many pre-trip searches occur up to 12 weeks before travel [6, 15]. Larger p_{max} values (e.g., 16–20) are hard to estimate on weekly data and tend to dilute the information and add noise. Smaller p_{max} values (e.g., 6–10) can miss useful longer lags. The indicator function ensures that only causal relationships contribute to the matrix C . This is reinforced by the observation that shorter lags typically indicate stronger causal relationships, as they suggest that the influence of one series on another is immediate [26]. The use of the inverse lag in the entry C_{ij} reflects this notion, where a shorter lag corresponds to a higher value of C_{ij} , emphasizing the immediacy and strength of the causal effect [47]. The term $1 + C$ is then multiplied element-wise (Hadamard product) with the similarity matrix $\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}$, meaning that the attention score $\frac{q_i k_j^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ between query q_i and key k_j is adjusted individually based on the causal relationship C_{ij} . This localized adjustment allows the attention mechanism to focus on specific causal interactions without affecting the entire similarity matrix.

After the element-wise multiplication, the softmax function normalizes the adjusted similarity matrix into a valid probability distribution. This process, detailed in step 3 of Algorithm 1, preserves the original attention mechanism’s ability to capture contextual relationships while incorporating causal information. As a result, the model learns both contextual and temporal causal relationships, providing a richer, causality-aware representation of the data.

4.4 Model Training and Evaluation

For model training, we employed the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1e-4 and a batch size of 64. We used Python 3.10.12 for programming. We present the complete layer structure of our model in Table 1. Alongside each layer, we provide the best values of hyperparameters.

Fig. 3. TimeSeriesSplit schema.

Fig. 4. Distribution of the sensors (in red points) in the study area.

To ensure a fair and robust comparison, we applied 10-fold **Cross-Validation (CV)** using the TimeSeriesSplit method, which evaluates model performance across different temporal segments of the data [7]. The CV process starts with 50% of the data for training and 20% for testing, incrementing the training size gradually up to 80%, while maintaining the test size fixed at 20%. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the training and testing sets across these 10 CV. To evaluate the model performance, we use the metrics: **Mean Absolute Error (MAE)**, **Mean Squared Error (MSE)**, and the coefficient of determination (R^2). Among these, R^2 serves as the primary basis for comparison, as it best captures the explanatory power of the models in predicting the target variable [13].

5 Case Study

This section presents our case study conducted in the Alpujarra region, located in southern Spain, which consists of three villages: Pampaneira, Capileira, and Bubión. This case study serves to evaluate the proposed method for predicting the weekly vehicle counts in the area.

The data collection process includes setting up the **Automatic Number Plate Recognition (ANPR)** devices, positioned as shown in Figure 4. We used four Hikvision IP cameras equipped with ANPR systems based on Deep Learning, see Figure 5. These devices have vehicle detection sensors, a 2MP resolution, 2.8–12 mm varifocal lenses, and IR LEDs with a range of 50 m. The ANPR cameras were positioned at the entry and exit points of each village to cover and monitor all vehicular traffic entering the area [8, 20].

The ANPR cameras recorded the license plates and timestamps of each vehicle passing through their coverage area. The dataset spans 24 months (from February 2022 to January 2024). After collecting the raw data, which includes the number plate, camera identifier, date, and direction (see Table 2), we applied a data cleaning process to recover missing digits in the plate number detections

Fig. 5. Automatic license plate recognition with IoT camera devices.

Table 2. Raw Dataset

Variable	Description	Source
num_plate	License plate number	ANPR cameras
camera_ID	Identifier for ANPR camera	ANPR cameras
date	Timestamp of appearance	ANPR cameras
direction	Direction of vehicle (entry or exit)	ANPR cameras

Table 3. Description of the Rural Case Study Dataset

Variable	Description		Source
date	Weekly dates from Feb 2022 to Jan 2024		ANPR cameras
vehicle_count	Weekly vehicle counts		ANPR cameras
	Group	Google Trends terms	
google_trends	Initial set of Google Trends terms	Pampaneira, Capileira, Bubión <i>(These refer to the main villages of the case study).</i>	Manually selected
	Expanded set of Google Trends terms	Trevélez, Trevélez Spain, Lanjarón Spain, Soportújar Spain, Órgiva Spain, Alpujarra, the Alpujarra granadina, Granada Alpujarra, villages of the Alpujarra, Granada Alpujarra vil-lages, Alpujarra Magna, rural house Granada <i>(These terms denote the broader geographical context of the study area, capturing related locations and regional searches focused on the entire area).</i>	PyTrends API

using the Damerau–Levenshtein distance algorithm [21]. Next, we aggregated the cleaned vehicle detections into weekly vehicle counts for the study area, which serve as the target variable Y in our forecasting model.

In addition to the vehicle count data, we enriched the dataset with relevant Google Trends time series obtained from the Google Trends platform.⁴ To that end, we began with an initial set of Google Trends terms describing the case study (see Table 3). We then expanded this set and obtained the associated weekly time series using the PyTrends API.⁵ These weekly time series serve as predictor variables $X = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{15}\}$ in our model, representing a total of 15 distinct weekly search queries, as shown in Table 3.

As an example, Figure 6 plots the Google Trends time series of the initial set of Google Trends terms from Table 3, alongside the weekly vehicle counts. The blue arrows highlight typical lead and lag patterns, where peaks in search interest tend to precede increases in vehicles by a few weeks, with seasonal variation. This initial set and the expanded set of terms serve as inputs to our methodology, where they are semantically validated with the BETO LM using the reference string

⁴<https://trends.google.es/trends/>.

⁵<https://pypi.org/project/pytrends/>.

Fig. 6. Weekly Google Trends time series for Pampaneira, Capileira, and Bubiión (left y -axis), together with vehicles per week entering the area (right y -axis). Dashed annotations indicate temporal shifts (lag) between peaks in relative search interest in Pampaneira and the subsequent increase in vehicle counts in the area.

Table 4. Traffic Volume Metrics by Temporal Scale and Location

	Daily				Weekly				Monthly			
	All region	Pampaneira	Bubiión	Capileira	All region	Pampaneira	Bubiión	Capileira	All region	Pampaneira	Bubiión	Capileira
Mean	1,349.3	1,322.0	1,256.1	1,191.8	9,444.8	9,253.9	8,792.8	8,342.6	39,290.6	38,496.3	36,578.1	34,705.0
Median	1,270	1,244	1,179	1,115	9,446	9,258	8,820	8,386	40,473	39,586	37,616	35,901
P25	975	952	912	867	8,112	7,969	7,506	7,137	36,102	35,382	33,646	31,939
P75	1,659	1,647	1,554	1,457	10,464	10,259	9,848	9,491	45,704	45,057	43,194	40,875
Min	333	329	307	283	3,459	3,400	3,177	3,054	36,857	34,100	31,177	30,254
Max	3,357	3,269	3,076	2,887	15,985	15,474	14,814	13,968	61,135	59,645	56,723	53,742
Std. dev.	492.1	483.3	459.5	433.8	2,206.3	2,157.9	2,055.8	1,947.3	11,107.8	10,861.1	10,292.6	9,707.1

The table reports descriptive statistics for the full study area (Alpujarra region) and for each town (Pampaneira, Bubiión, Capileira) at daily, weekly, and monthly aggregation levels.

“Turismo rural en la Alpujarra” (see Equation (6)). We then generate lagged candidates and retain only those that pass both the Granger causality test and the correlation test (see Equations (7) and (8)). The resulting validated, lagged time series serve as the predictor variables for the GCT architecture.

6 Results and Discussion

This section evaluates the proposed GCT methodology. We first present descriptive statistics of the dataset to establish the baseline characteristics of the traffic patterns in the study region. Table 4 reports traffic indicators at daily, weekly, and monthly scales for the Alpujarra region, where the total resident population was 1,209 according to the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE).⁶ Although data are collected at multiple temporal scales, we use weekly aggregations to align with Google Trends time series.

Following this descriptive analysis, we conduct a series of experiments to validate the GCT architecture. We begin in Section 6.1 with a sensitivity analysis to justify our selection of pre-processing hyperparameters. Section 6.2 presents the main experimental results for our rural case study, comparing GCT against all baselines. We then conduct an ablation study in Section 6.3 to analyze the individual contributions of our model’s key components. To validate the model’s

⁶<https://www.ine.es>.

Table 5. Sensitivity Analysis over the Cosine-Similarity Threshold τ and the Correlation Threshold α , Starting from 15 Original Google Trends Terms (Table 3)

τ (Equation (6))	α (Equation (8))	Semantically validated terms (Equation (6))	Lagged series ($p_{\max} = 12$)	Pass Granger p-value < 0.05 (Equation (7))	Final time series Correlation filter (Equation (8))	MAE (\pm SD)	MSE (\pm SD)	R^2 (\pm SD)	Time (s) (\pm SD)
0.25	0.25	15	180	48	26	0.0490 \pm 0.0150	0.0040 \pm 0.0021	0.704 \pm 0.192	29.35 \pm 0.96
0.25	0.50	15	180	48	20	0.0460 \pm 0.0146	0.0035 \pm 0.0019	0.742 \pm 0.165	27.85 \pm 0.80
0.25	0.75	15	180	48	13	0.0558 \pm 0.0163	0.0053 \pm 0.0023	0.615 \pm 0.240	25.90 \pm 0.70
0.50	0.25	12	144	40	22	0.0433 \pm 0.0159	0.0037 \pm 0.0024	0.760 \pm 0.155	28.15 \pm 0.84
0.50	0.50	12	144	40	20	0.0438 \pm 0.0143	0.0032 \pm 0.0019	0.773 \pm 0.132	27.37 \pm 0.71
0.50	0.75	12	144	40	14	0.0451 \pm 0.0148	0.0034 \pm 0.0020	0.751 \pm 0.140	26.45 \pm 0.71
0.75	0.25	8	96	24	14	0.0516 \pm 0.0155	0.0045 \pm 0.0022	0.665 \pm 0.195	27.05 \pm 0.77
0.75	0.50	8	96	24	12	0.0469 \pm 0.0149	0.0037 \pm 0.0020	0.735 \pm 0.150	26.20 \pm 0.69
0.75	0.75	8	96	24	8	0.0604 \pm 0.0167	0.0061 \pm 0.0025	0.546 \pm 0.260	24.80 \pm 0.62

Semantically validated terms are Google Trends terms retained by the semantic validation step via cosine similarity with the reference string using the selected LM (Equation (6)). Lagged series are the number of semantically validated terms multiplied by p_{\max} , with $p_{\max} = 12$. Pass Granger (p-value < 0.05) counts lagged series with significant Granger causality (Equation (7)). Final time series are those that pass the final correlation filter (Equation (8)). Metrics are mean \pm SD over the 10 folds. Bold values indicate the best results.

robustness, we evaluate its performance in a new setting in Section 6.4. Finally, we synthesize all findings in Section 6.5.

6.1 Sensitivity Analysis

We conduct a sensitivity analysis for the case study to assess how the semantic filter threshold τ (Equation (6)) and the correlation threshold α (Equation (8)) affect both predictive performance and computational cost. Starting from the 15 original Google Trends terms in Table 3, we vary $\tau \in \{0.25, 0.50, 0.75\}$ and keep only those terms whose cosine similarity with the study-area reference string is at least τ . For every semantically validated term, we obtain its weekly Google Trends time series, generate up to $p_{\max} = 12$ weekly lags, and test each lagged time series for Granger causality against the target series Y_t (Equation (7)). The column Pass Granger p-value < 0.05 in Table 5 reports the number of lagged series that are significant. We then apply the correlation screen $|\text{Corr}(X_{t-i}, Y_t)| > \alpha$ with $\alpha \in \{0.25, 0.50, 0.75\}$ to those same Google Trends time series; the column Final time series counts the Google Trends time series that pass both filters.

As shown in Table 5, the configuration of $\tau = 0.5$ and $\alpha = 0.5$ yielded the best predictive performance (highest R^2 and lowest MSE). Furthermore, the semantic similarity threshold ($\tau = 0.5$) is consistent with its use in related literature [36], and the correlation threshold ($\alpha = 0.5$) is also consistent with conventional cutoffs for strong linear association [1]. Hence, we fixed $\tau = 0.5$ and $\alpha = 0.5$ for our experiments.

6.2 Results

For evaluation, we compared our methodology with various baseline algorithms in both univariate and multivariate settings using CV. In the univariate case, we implemented ARIMA, GRU, LSTM, LSTM with a multi-head attention layer, and TimesFM [17]. For the multivariate setting, we included ARIMAX (the multivariate extension of ARIMA), Multivariate GRU, Multivariate LSTM, Multivariate Conv1D with LSTM [42], cMLP and cLSTM [59], CausalFormer [32], and Moirai [63]. In the univariate cases, the method uses only the historical values of the target variable Y . In the multivariate cases, the method uses past values of the target variable Y along with Google Trends time series data as external predictor variables.

The results are presented in Table 6 and Figure 7. The statistical models (ARIMA, ARIMAX) showed lower R^2 scores, of -0.1552 and 0.1029 , respectively. Univariate models, such as GRU, LSTM, and LSTM with Attention, demonstrated moderate performance, with average R^2 scores ranging

Table 6. CV Performance—Methods with Execution Times—Rural Case Study

Model	Metric (\pm Std Dev)			
	MAE	MSE	R^2	Time (s)
ARIMA	0.0982 \pm 0.0143	0.0155 \pm 0.0036	-0.1552 \pm 0.2342	0.8981 \pm 0.1022
ARIMAX	0.0865 \pm 0.0125	0.0119 \pm 0.0030	0.1029 \pm 0.2484	0.4096 \pm 0.0415
Univariate GRU	0.0712 \pm 0.0258	0.0085 \pm 0.0049	0.3847 \pm 0.3085	19.0396 \pm 0.7736
Multivariate GRU	0.0910 \pm 0.0164	0.0141 \pm 0.0068	-0.1300 \pm 0.7257	21.9710 \pm 0.2746
Univariate LSTM	0.0684 \pm 0.0134	0.0084 \pm 0.0036	0.3922 \pm 0.2332	18.9211 \pm 0.2085
Univariate LSTM with attention	0.0627 \pm 0.0217	0.0073 \pm 0.0051	0.4596 \pm 0.3423	23.6318 \pm 1.0318
Multivariate LSTM	0.0866 \pm 0.0223	0.0122 \pm 0.0096	0.0280 \pm 0.7968	21.4400 \pm 0.6348
Multivariate Conv1d+LSTM [42]	0.0718 \pm 0.0168	0.0083 \pm 0.0035	0.3555 \pm 0.3284	18.9420 \pm 0.3810
TimesFM [17]	0.0810 \pm 0.0086	0.0107 \pm 0.0026	0.2542 \pm 0.1188	1.70 \pm 0.1969
Moirai [63]	0.1067 \pm 0.0246	0.0183 \pm 0.0070	0.0896 \pm 0.1963	5.01 \pm 0.2232
cLSTM [59]	0.1400 \pm 0.0347	0.0464 \pm 0.0205	-0.7696 \pm 0.9802	10.33 \pm 0.6386
cMLP [59]	0.0955 \pm 0.0157	0.0161 \pm 0.0048	0.0455 \pm 0.1703	1.61 \pm 0.6030
CausalFormer [32]	0.0783 \pm 0.0084	0.0101 \pm 0.0018	0.2891 \pm 0.1300	8.49 \pm 0.4633
GCT (Our model)	0.0438 \pm 0.0143	0.0032 \pm 0.0019	0.7734 \pm 0.1323	27.37 \pm 0.7053

Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Fig. 7. Comparison of R^2 results.

from 0.3847 to 0.4596. The multivariate GRU and LSTM models showed slight improvements over their univariate counterparts but did not reach the performance levels of our proposed model. Large foundation models showed mixed results. Moirai achieved an R^2 of 0.0896, while TimesFM performed better ($R^2 = 0.2542$), which is expected given its pre-training on Google Trends data. However, both foundation models fell significantly short compared to causality-aware approaches, such as CausalFormer and GCT. However, they yield faster execution times (1.70 s for TimesFM, 5.01 s for Moirai), as they lack explicit causal relationship modeling. The cLSTM model performed poorly, even worse than the statistical models. cMLP performed better than cLSTM but still did not achieve good R^2 scores. CausalFormer showed slightly higher R^2 values compared to previous methods but did not exceed the 0.5 R^2 threshold. Our model achieved the lowest MAE of 0.0438, the lowest MSE of 0.0032, and the highest R^2 score of 0.7734, indicating a better fit to the data compared with the other evaluated models. These results represent improvements of 30% in MAE, 56% in MSE, and 68% in R^2 compared to the univariate LSTM with attention, the second-best model.

Table 7. CV Performance—Ablation Test

Model	Metric (\pm Std Dev)			
	MAE	MSE	R^2	Time (s)
Full Model	0.0438 \pm 0.0143	0.0032 \pm 0.0019	0.7734 \pm 0.1323	27.37 \pm 0.7888
Without Causality	0.0811 \pm 0.0291	0.0107 \pm 0.00697	0.2056 \pm 0.4920	28.07 \pm 0.2746
Without Correlation	0.0794 \pm 0.0095	0.0097 \pm 0.0028	0.3088 \pm 0.4920	29.33 \pm 0.2746
Without Attention Mask	0.0601 \pm 0.0194	0.0060 \pm 0.0041	0.5600 \pm 0.3056	28.88 \pm 0.9250
Without Causality and Correlation	0.0777 \pm 0.0163	0.0104 \pm 0.0048	0.1964 \pm 0.4411	29.21 \pm 0.8247
Without Causality and Attention Mask	0.1067 \pm 0.0360	0.0167 \pm 0.0100	-0.2059 \pm 0.6280	27.88 \pm 0.9632
Without Correlation and Attention Mask	0.0933 \pm 0.0283	0.0149 \pm 0.0076	-0.0916 \pm 0.6744	29.12 \pm 0.6980
Base_model	0.0769 \pm 0.0117	0.0100 \pm 0.0040	0.2514 \pm 0.2653	29.21 \pm 1.0849

Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Fig. 8. R^2 score distribution for different methods.

Execution times were longer for our model, averaging 27.37, compared to the other algorithms, which required at most 23.63 seconds. However, this additional computation time is compensated by the consistently superior performance of our model across all metrics, as observed in nearly all CV folds, as shown in Table 6 and Figure 7.

6.3 Ablation Test

We analyzed the proposed method with different configurations to explore how the inclusion or exclusion of causality filtering (Equation (7)), correlation filtering (Equation (8)), and the causal attention mask (Equation (9)) affects the model’s performance. These components correspond to the red boxes in Figure 1. This analysis allowed us to quantify the effect of each component, both individually and in combination. The full model corresponds to our proposed methodology, incorporating causality filtering, correlation filtering, and the causality mask in the GCT architecture. To evaluate the impact of these components, we progressively removed each feature, ultimately reaching a base model that lacks all three components.

We can see in Table 7 and Figure 8 that the full model achieves the lowest average MAE of 0.0438, the lowest MSE of 0.0032, and the highest R^2 score of 0.7734. These results reflect the model’s strong predictive accuracy and explanatory power (see Figures 9 and 10 for the learning curves).

Fig. 9. Train loss for ablation study.

Fig. 10. Validation loss for ablation study.

Removing any single element leads to a decline in performance compared to the full model. Removing causality or correlation filtering increases error metrics, with the removal of causality showing the greatest effect, up to 0.2056 on average R^2 . Disabling the causality mask also produces worse results, confirming the value of incorporating the causal mask into the attention layer. When two components are removed simultaneously, the model's performance declines further. Configurations lacking the causality mask and another component yield the highest MAE and MSE values, along with an R^2 near 0 (see the purple and brown boxplots in Figure 8), performing even worse than the base model.

Overall, removing causality, correlation, or the transformer mechanism individually leads to a noticeable decline in the model's predictive accuracy and explanatory power. Furthermore, the simultaneous removal of multiple components results in a compounded decrease in performance, underscoring the synergistic contributions of causality, correlation, and the transformer mask to the model's effectiveness.

Fig. 11. Case study of Salt Lake City.

6.4 Case Study: Generalizability of the Methodology

To validate the robustness and generalizability of our methodology, we applied the entire pipeline to a second case study: Salt Lake City, Utah (USA). For this study, we sourced traffic data from the Utah Department of Transportation (UDOT), which operates non-intrusive, side-fire radar stations providing vehicle counts.⁷ We selected four stations located on the main roads to the city (North, South, East, and West) and aggregated their data into weekly total counts to serve as the target variable Y . Figure 11 shows the study area and the selected station locations.

To study visitation demand, we started with an initial set of five Google Trends terms specific to the new case study: “Salt Lake City,” “Weather in Salt Lake City,” “Salt Lake City airport,” “Great Salt Lake,” and “Twin Peaks.” We then expanded this initial set using the PyTrends API, obtaining a total of 172 time series.

Next, we proceeded with the semantic validation of the expanded set. Since this corpus is in English, we used BERT (base, uncased) to ensure the tokenizer and embedding space were aligned with the data’s linguistic context. We used the reference string “Salt Lake City visitor attractions and travel” for this validation step (see Equation (6)). Following our methodology, we generated lagged series and filtered them using the Granger causality test (Equation (7)) and the correlation test (Equation (8)).

We then trained the same set of baseline models and our GCT architecture under the identical 10-fold TimeSeriesSplit CV scheme. The resulting metrics are reported in Table 8 and Figure 12. As shown in Table 8, GCT again achieves the best performance across all metrics, obtaining the highest R^2 score (0.5058) and the lowest MAE (0.0501) and MSE (0.0037). This represents an R^2 improvement of 47.4% over the next-best performing baseline, the Univariate LSTM with Attention ($R^2 = 0.3432$), and a 52.5% improvement over TimesFM ($R^2 = 0.3317$). These results confirm the model’s robustness and its ability to generalize effectively to the new context.

⁷<https://www.udot.utah.gov/connect/business/traffic-data/>.

Table 8. CV Performance—Methods with Execution Times—Salt Lake City

Model	Metric (\pm Std Dev)			
	MAE	MSE	R^2	Time (s)
ARIMA	0.1540 \pm 0.0215	0.0250 \pm 0.0723	-0.2425 \pm 0.3322	1.1639 \pm 0.1419
ARIMAX	0.1343 \pm 0.0246	0.0186 \pm 0.0054	0.0147 \pm 0.2260	0.8832 \pm 0.0374
Univariate GRU	0.1120 \pm 0.0623	0.0168 \pm 0.0110	0.1563 \pm 0.1755	21.2521 \pm 3.0565
Multivariate GRU	0.1632 \pm 0.0083	0.0270 \pm 0.0052	-0.2799 \pm 0.3287	24.9496 \pm 2.6463
Univariate LSTM	0.1530 \pm 0.0199	0.0245 \pm 0.0044	-0.2415 \pm 0.0569	22.6211 \pm 0.1947
Univariate LSTM with Attention	0.0910 \pm 0.0251	0.0125 \pm 0.0062	0.3432 \pm 0.2110	30.5435 \pm 1.1426
Multivariate LSTM	0.1410 \pm 0.0259	0.0215 \pm 0.0083	-0.0802 \pm 0.3735	30.4370 \pm 0.6659
Multivariate Conv1d+LSTM [42]	0.1680 \pm 0.0195	0.0285 \pm 0.0041	-0.3340 \pm 0.3562	26.9420 \pm 0.3810
Moirai [63]	0.1350 \pm 0.0262	0.0190 \pm 0.0080	0.0096 \pm 0.2385	5.6800 \pm 0.0929
TimesFM [17]	0.0932 \pm 0.0118	0.0133 \pm 0.0051	0.3317 \pm 0.1712	2.5020 \pm 0.4969
cLSTM [59]	0.1450 \pm 0.0401	0.0225 \pm 0.0235	-0.1215 \pm 0.2365	13.3290 \pm 0.6383
cMLP [59]	0.1480 \pm 0.0180	0.0230 \pm 0.0057	-0.1481 \pm 0.1660	2.2050 \pm 0.6029
CausalFormer [32]	0.1050 \pm 0.0127	0.0155 \pm 0.0027	0.2261 \pm 0.2108	9.3530 \pm 0.7064
GCT (Our model)	0.0501 \pm 0.0164	0.0037 \pm 0.0022	0.5058 \pm 0.1327	36.9810 \pm 2.2605

Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Fig. 12. Comparison of R^2 results—Salt Lake City.

6.5 Discussion

The comparison across statistical and deep learning models, both in their univariate and multivariate cases, provides insights into their capabilities and limitations. As summarized in our first case study (Table 6), statistical models (ARIMA, ARIMAX) performed poorly, with low or even negative R^2 scores, likely due to their linear nature and inability to capture complex, non-linear patterns in the data. Univariate deep learning models, such as GRU, LSTM, and LSTM with Attention, showed improvements with R^2 scores between 0.3847 and 0.4596. However, their limited capacity to incorporate contextual information constrains their explanatory power. Multivariate GRU and LSTM models achieved marginally better scores but remained low; see Figure 7, indicating their limitations in capturing the dataset's full complexity. Causality-aware methods, such as cLSTM and cMLP, also fail to adequately fit these data, as evidenced by their poor average R^2 values (-0.7696 for cLSTM and 0.0455 for cMLP). These architectures lack attention mechanisms and

consequently cannot capture the complex temporal relationships present in real time series, limiting their predictive capacity. CausalFormer, which incorporates attention, proves insufficient for these data, achieving an average R^2 of 0.289. CausalFormer accepts input from a single predefined observation window and cannot identify multi-scale causal patterns [32], which is a significant limitation in this analysis. Our proposed model surpasses all models across all metrics. The lower MAE (0.0438), lower MSE (0.0032), and higher R^2 (0.7734) than other solutions indicate a better fit to the data, due to the model's ability to integrate and effectively capture both contextual and causal relationships. This adaptability allows it to explain a higher variance in the data, providing more reliable predictions. Despite its longer execution time (averaging 27.37 seconds compared to other algorithms, which required at most 23.63 seconds), the improvement in performance justifies this tradeoff.

To test the method's robustness, we further evaluated its generalizability in the second context of Salt Lake City (Table 8). This scenario proved more challenging, as most baseline models, including standard multivariate deep learning approaches, yielded negative R^2 scores. The best-performing baselines were the large foundation models, TimesFM ($R^2 = 0.3317$), and the Univariate LSTM with Attention ($R^2 = 0.3432$). Once again, our proposed GCT architecture significantly outperformed all other methods, achieving the highest R^2 score (0.5058) and the lowest errors (MAE 0.0501, MSE 0.0037). This represents a 47.4% increase in R^2 compared to the next-best baseline. The consistent success of GCT in both a sparse, rural setting (Alpujarra, Spain) and a dense setting (Salt Lake City, USA) highlights the robustness of our methodology.

6.6 Limitations and Future Work

Although the results provide a superior performance with respect to the baseline methods, the proposed methodology has some limitations. First, the multi-step pre-processing and the complexity of GCT increase training time, which can cause delays when using large datasets or real-time applications. Second, the use of a Granger-based linear screening method serves only as a filtering step to select relevant inputs. The retained signals are then modeled by the non-linear GCT architecture (LSTM and Transformer), which is designed to capture complex, non-linear interactions. Performance in scenarios dominated by purely non-linear relationships may still require careful lag selection and more extensive hyperparameter tuning. Third, even though leveraging Google Trends offers a valuable, publicly available proxy for behavioral dynamics, GCT's reliance on this source limits portability to regions with low Google adoption (e.g., China, Russia).

Additionally, with respect to the data used, our methodology could be extended to support other datasets, such as forecasting, land use features, and road network features, which can be helpful to improve the prediction accuracy. Unfortunately, for our rural case study, we could not find reliable datasets. The region lacks a local meteorological station, and triangulated estimates in mountains with microclimates proved too noisy for reliable integration. Similarly, there are no open datasets with sufficient spatial/temporal resolution for land use or network topology in the area. Given these constraints, we prioritized publicly accessible Google Trends time series and did not include these other external datasets in our methodology. Another limitation stems from the destination-wide scope of our methodology. The model is designed to forecast the total aggregated weekly vehicle counts to a study area, aiming to capture destination-wide level demand, because normally tourists go to different spots in the area. Consequently, it does not disaggregate or model the fine-grained mobility within that area, such as per-location forecasts.

As future work, we aim to optimize pre-processing and model design to improve scalability and real-time performance. Working with the Alpujarra region council, we plan to install additional sensors (e.g., a local weather station) to support multimodal sensor fusion. Finally, we will extend

the methodology to support fine-grained, per-location forecasts, which would be especially useful in areas with distinct intra-destination spots.

7 Conclusion

This study presents GCT, a transformer-based architecture that incorporates a causal mask to modify the attention similarity weight matrix. This causal mask uses Granger Causality tests to identify causal relationships among inputs in a multivariate NN, adjusting the attention weights accordingly. By doing so, the GCT ensures that the model focuses not only on the temporal similarities captured by the attention mechanism but also on the causal relationships among inputs.

To validate this proposal, we designed a methodology that includes an initial feature validation step using a LM, followed by a feature selection step based on causal and correlation filters, and finally a prediction model using our GCT architecture. We first applied this methodology to a case study for predicting weekly vehicle counts in a rural area. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed approach outperforms other statistical and deep learning models, achieving improvements of up to 30% in MAE, 56% in MSE, and 68% in R^2 compared to the best-performing baseline method. Furthermore, we confirmed the method's generalizability in a second case study (Salt Lake City), where GCT again significantly outperformed all baselines, achieving a 47% increase in R^2 over the strongest competitor. The consistent success in both contexts validates the robustness and wide applicability of our approach.

References

- [1] Jeremy Adler and Ingela Parmryd. 2010. Quantifying colocalization by correlation: The Pearson correlation coefficient is superior to the Mander's overlap coefficient. *Cytometry Part A* 77, 8 (2010), 733–742.
- [2] Usman Ahmed, Jerry Chun-Wei Lin, and Gautam Srivastava. 2023. Multivariate time-series sensor vital sign forecasting of cardiovascular and chronic respiratory diseases. *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems* 38 (2023), 100868. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.suscom.2023.100868>
- [3] Abdul Fatir Ansari, Lorenzo Stella, Caner Turkmen, Xiyuan Zhang, Pedro Mercado, Huibin Shen, Oleksandr Shchur, Syama Sundar Rangapuram, Sebastian Pineda Arango, Shubham Kapoor, et al. 2024. Chronos: Learning the language of time series. arXiv:2403.07815. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.07815>
- [4] Ahmad O. Aseeri. 2023. Effective RNN-based forecasting methodology design for improving short-term power load forecasts: Application to large-scale power-grid time series. *Journal of Computational Science* 68 (2023), 101984. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2023.101984>
- [5] Jimmy Lei Ba, Jamie Ryan Kiros, and Geoffrey E. Hinton. 2016. Layer normalization. arXiv:1607.06450. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1607.06450>
- [6] Prosper F. Bangwayo-Skeete and Ryan W. Skeete. 2015. Can Google data improve the forecasting performance of tourist arrivals? Mixed-data sampling approach. *Tourism Management* 46 (2015), 454–464.
- [7] Daniel Berrar. 2019. Cross-validation. *Encyclopedia of Bioinformatics and Computational Biology* 1 (2019), 542–545. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809633-8.20349-X>
- [8] Daniel Bolaños-Martínez, Maria Bermudez-Edo, Jose Luis Garrido, and Blanca L. Delgado-Márquez. 2024. Spatio-temporal dynamics of vehicles: Fusion of traffic data and context information. *Data in Brief* 53 (2024), 110084. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.110084>
- [9] Daniel Bolaños-Martínez, Alberto Durán-López, Jose Luis Garrido, Blanca Delgado-Márquez, and Maria Bermudez-Edo. 2025. SASD: Self-attention for small datasets—A case study in smart villages. *Expert Systems with Applications* 271 (2025), 126245. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.126245>
- [10] Stephan B. Bruns and David I. Stern. 2019. Lag length selection and p-hacking in granger causality testing: Prevalence and performance of meta-regression models. *Empirical Economics* 56 (2019), 797–830.
- [11] José Cañete, Gabriel Chaperon, Rodrigo Fuentes, Jou-Hui Ho, Hojin Kang, and Jorge Pérez. 2023. Spanish pre-trained BERT model and evaluation data. arXiv:2308.02976. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2308.02976>
- [12] Nisha Singh Chauhan and Neetesh Kumar. 2024. Confined attention mechanism enabled recurrent neural network framework to improve traffic flow prediction. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 136 (2024), 108791. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2024.108791>

- [13] Davide Chicco, Matthijs J. Warrens, and Giuseppe Jurman. 2021. The coefficient of determination R-squared is more informative than SMAPE, MAE, MAPE, MSE and RMSE in regression analysis evaluation. *PeerJ. Computer Science* 7 (2021), e623. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.623>
- [14] Hyunyoung Choi and Hal Varian. 2012. Predicting the present with Google trends. *Economic Record* 88 (2012), 2–9.
- [15] Uwimana Claude. 2020. Predicting tourism demands by google trends: A hidden Markov models based study. *Journal of System and Management Sciences* 10, 1 (2020), 106–120.
- [16] Zhiyong Cui, Ruimin Ke, Ziyuan Pu, and Yinhai Wang. 2020. Stacked bidirectional and unidirectional LSTM recurrent neural network for forecasting network-wide traffic state with missing values. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 118 (2020), 102674.
- [17] Abhimanyu Das, Weihao Kong, Rajat Sen, and Yichen Zhou. 2024. A decoder-only foundation model for time-series forecasting. In *Proceedings of the 41st International Conference on Machine Learning*, Vol. 235, PMLR, 10148–10167.
- [18] Suparna De, Maria Bermudez-Edo, Honghui Xu, and Zhipeng Cai. 2022. Deep generative models in the industrial Internet of Things: A survey. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 18, 9 (2022), 5728–5737. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2022.3155656>
- [19] Jacob Devlin. 2018. BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. arXiv:1810.04805. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>
- [20] Alberto Durán-López, Daniel Bolaños-Martinez, Zaid Almahmoud, Chandresh Pravin, Suparna De, and Maria Bermudez-Edo. 2025. Route optimization in smart villages: A graph neural network approach. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 12, 21 (2025). DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1109/jiot.2025.3599235>
- [21] Alberto Durán-López, Daniel Bolaños-Martinez, Luisa Delgado-Márquez, and Maria Bermudez-Edo. 2024. RouteRecoverer: A tool to create routes and recover noisy license plate number data. *Software Impacts* 20 (2024), 100636. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpa.2024.100636>
- [22] Panagiotis Fafoutellis and Eleni I. Vlahogianni. 2025. A theory-informed multivariate causal framework for trustworthy short-term urban traffic forecasting. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 170 (2025), 104945.
- [23] Francisco M. Garcia-Moreno, Marta Badenes-Sastre, Francisca Expósito, Maria Jose Rodriguez-Fortiz, and Maria Bermudez-Edo. 2025. EEG headbands vs caps: How many electrodes do I need to detect emotions? The case of the MUSE headband. *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 184 (2025), 109463.
- [24] Azul Garza, Cristian Challu, and Max Mergenthaler-Canseco. 2023. TimeGPT-1. arXiv:2310.03589. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.03589>
- [25] Clive W. J. Granger. 1969. Investigating causal relations by econometric models and cross-spectral methods. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society* 37, 3 (1969), 424–438.
- [26] Moritz Günther, Jan W. Kantelhardt, and Ronny P. Bartsch. 2022. The reconstruction of causal networks in physiology. *Frontiers in Network Physiology* 2 (2022), 893743. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnetp.2022.893743>
- [27] Ziheng Huang, Dujuan Wang, Yunqiang Yin, and T. C. E. Cheng. 2025. A prediction interval framework-based spatial-temporal convolution block network for traffic demand prediction. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 204 (2025), 104426.
- [28] Basharat Hussain, Muhammad Khalil Afzal, Shafiq Ahmad, and Almetwally M. Mostafa. 2021. Intelligent traffic flow prediction using optimized GRU model. *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), 100736–100746.
- [29] R. J. Hyndman. 2018. *Forecasting: Principles and Practice* (2nd ed.). OTexts.
- [30] Chukwutoo C. Ihueze and Uchendu O. Onwurah. 2018. Road traffic accidents prediction modelling: An analysis of Anambra state, Nigeria. *Accident Analysis & Prevention* 112 (2018), 21–29.
- [31] Ayad Ghany Ismaeel, Krishnadas Janardhanan, Manishankar Sankar, Yuvaraj Natarajan, Sarmad Nozad Mahmood, Sameer Alani, and Akram H. Shather. 2023. Traffic pattern classification in smart cities using deep recurrent neural network. *Sustainability* 15, 19 (2023), 14522.
- [32] Lingbai Kong, Wengen Li, Hanchen Yang, Yichao Zhang, Jihong Guan, and Shuigeng Zhou. 2024. CausalFormer: An interpretable transformer for temporal causal discovery. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 37, 1 (2024), 102–115.
- [33] T. Kudo. 2018. SentencePiece: A simple and language independent subword tokenizer and detokenizer for neural text processing. arXiv:1808.06226. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.06226>
- [34] Praveen B. Kumar and K. Hariharan. 2022. Time series traffic flow prediction with hyper-parameter optimized ARIMA models for intelligent transportation system. *Journal of Scientific & Industrial Research* 81, 4 (2022), 408–415.
- [35] Raghavendra Kumar, Pardeep Kumar, and Yugal Kumar. 2020. Time series data prediction using IoT and machine learning technique. *Procedia Computer Science* 167 (2020), 373–381. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.03.240>
- [36] Wai Ching Leung, Shira Wein, and Nathan Schneider. 2022. Semantic similarity as a window into vector-and graph-based metrics. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Natural Language Generation, Evaluation, and Metrics (GEM '22)*, 106–115.

- [37] Guanzhi Li, Aining Zhang, Qizhi Zhang, Di Wu, and Choujun Zhan. 2022. Pearson correlation coefficient-based performance enhancement of broad learning system for stock price prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs* 69, 5 (2022), 2413–2417. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tcsii.2022.3160266>
- [38] Hongyi Li. 2024. Traffic flow prediction based on nonlinear weight decreasing PSO-SVR univariate time series prediction algorithm. *Applied and Computational Engineering* 75, 7 (2024), 237–242. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54254/2755-2721/75/20240544>
- [39] Zhouhan Lin, Minwei Feng, Cicero Nogueira dos Santos, Mo Yu, Bing Xiang, Bowen Zhou, and Yoshua Bengio. 2017. A structured self-attentive sentence embedding. arXiv:1703.03130. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1703.03130>
- [40] Zhaolong Ling, Enqi Xu, Peng Zhou, Liang Du, Kui Yu, and Xindong Wu. 2024. Fair feature selection: A causal perspective. *ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data* 18, 7 (2024), 1–23.
- [41] Boyi Liu, Xiangyan Tang, Jieren Cheng, and Pengchao Shi. 2020. Traffic flow combination forecasting method based on improved LSTM and ARIMA. *International Journal of Embedded Systems* 12, 1 (2020), 22–30. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJES.2020.105287>
- [42] Chan Li Long, Yash Guleria, and Sameer Alam. 2021. Air passenger forecasting using neural Granger causal Google trend queries. *Journal of Air Transport Management* 95 (2021), 102083. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2021.102083>
- [43] S. Narmadha and V. Vijayakumar. 2023. Spatio-temporal vehicle traffic flow prediction using multivariate CNN and LSTM model. *Materials Today: Proceedings* 81 (2023), 826–833.
- [44] Hrvoje Novak, Filip Bronić, Anđelko Kolak, and Vinko Lešić. 2023. Data-driven modeling of urban traffic travel times for short-and long-term forecasting. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 24, 10 (2023), 11198–11209.
- [45] Irem Önder. 2017. Forecasting tourism demand with Google trends: Accuracy comparison of countries versus cities. *International Journal of Tourism Research* 19, 6 (2017), 648–660.
- [46] Konstantinos G. Papaspyropoulos and Dimitris Kugiumtzis. 2024. On the validity of Granger causality for ecological count time series. *Econometrics* 12, 2 (2024), 13. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/econometrics12020013>
- [47] Wei Peng. 2020. DL: A deep learning-based Granger causality inference. *Complexity* 2020, 1 (2020), 5960171. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5960171>
- [48] Kadiyala Ramana, Gautam Srivastava, Madapuri Rudra Kumar, Thippa Reddy Gadekallu, Jerry Chun-Wei Lin, Mamoun Alazab, and Celestine Iwendi. 2023. A vision transformer approach for traffic congestion prediction in urban areas. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 24, 4 (2023), 3922–3934.
- [49] Mohan Raparthy and Babu Dodda. 2023. Predictive maintenance in IoT devices using time series analysis and deep learning. *Danda Xuebao/Journal of Ballistics* 35, 1–10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.52783/dxjb.v35.113>
- [50] Kashif Rasul, Arjun Ashok, Andrew Robert Williams, Arian Khorasani, George Adamopoulos, Rishika Bhagwatkar, Marin Biloš, Hena Ghonia, Nadhir Hassen, Anderson Schneider, et al. 2023. Lag-Llama: Towards foundation models for time series forecasting. R0-FoMo: Robustness of few-shot and zero-shot learning in large foundation models. arXiv:2310.08278v3. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.08278v3>
- [51] N. Reimers. 2019. Sentence-BERT: Sentence embeddings using Siamese BERT-networks. arXiv:1908.10084. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.10084>
- [52] Selim Reza, Marta Campos Ferreira, José J. M. Machado, and João Manuel R. S. Tavares. 2022. A multi-head attention-based transformer model for traffic flow forecasting with a comparative analysis to recurrent neural networks. *Expert Systems with Applications* 202 (2022), 117275. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.117275>
- [53] Hasim Sak, Andrew W. Senior, Françoise Beaufays, et al. 2014. Long short-term memory recurrent neural network architectures for large scale acoustic modeling. In *Interspeech*, Vol. 2014, 338–342.
- [54] Reem Salman, Ayman Alzaatreh, and Hana Sulieman. 2022. The stability of different aggregation techniques in ensemble feature selection. *Journal of Big Data* 9, 1 (2022), 51.
- [55] Siroos Shahriari, Milad Ghasri, S. A. Sisson, and Taha Rashidi. 2020. Ensemble of ARIMA: Combining parametric and bootstrapping technique for traffic flow prediction. *Transportmetrica A: Transport Science* 16, 3 (2020), 1552–1573. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23249935.2020.1764662>
- [56] Nitish Srivastava, Geoffrey Hinton, Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, and Ruslan Salakhutdinov. 2014. Dropout: A simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research* 15, 1 (2014), 1929–1958.
- [57] Andrzej Sroczynski and Andrzej Czyzewski. 2023. Road traffic can be predicted by machine learning equally effectively as by complex microscopic model. *Scientific Reports* 13, 1 (2023), 14523. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-41902-y>
- [58] Yingchen Su and Yinna Ye. 2020. Daily passenger volume prediction in the bus transportation system using ARIMAX model with big data. In *Proceedings of the 2020 International Conference on Cyber-Enabled Distributed Computing and Knowledge Discovery (CyberC)*. IEEE, 291–300.
- [59] Alex Tank, Ian Covert, Nicholas Foti, Ali Shojaie, and Emily B. Fox. 2021. Neural granger causality. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 44, 8 (2021), 4267–4279. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3065601>

- [60] Ran Tian, Chu Wang, Jia Hu, and Zhongyu Ma. 2023. Multi-scale spatial-temporal aware transformer for C. *Information Sciences* 648 (2023), 119557.
- [61] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Łukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. 2017. Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Vol. 30.
- [62] Chao Wang and Yang Zhou. 2024. Rethinking the role of attention mechanism: A causality perspective. *Applied Intelligence* 54, 2 (2024), 1862–1878.
- [63] Gerald Woo, Chenghao Liu, Akshat Kumar, Caiming Xiong, Silvio Savarese, and Doyen Sahoo. 2024. Unified training of universal time series forecasting transformers. In *Proceedings of the 41st International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML '24)*. ACM, 53140–53164.
- [64] Yi Xiao, Xueting Tian, and Ming Xiao. 2020. Tourism traffic demand prediction using Google trends based on EEMD-DBN. *Engineering* 12, 3 (2020), 194–215. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4236/eng.2020.123016>
- [65] Xing Jiping. 2022. Estimating traffic volumes in an urban network based on taxi GPS and limited LPR data using machine learning techniques. In *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC '22)*. IEEE, 20–25. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC55140.2022.9922445>
- [66] Weiran Yao and Sean Qian. 2021. From Twitter to traffic predictor: Next-day morning traffic prediction using social media data. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 124 (2021), 102938.
- [67] Kui Yu, Xianjie Guo, Lin Liu, Jiuyong Li, Hao Wang, Zhaolong Ling, and Xindong Wu. 2020. Causality-based feature selection: Methods and evaluations. *ACM Computing Surveys* 53, 5 (2020), 1–36.
- [68] Yong Yu, Xiaosheng Si, Changhua Hu, and Jianxun Zhang. 2019. A review of recurrent neural networks: LSTM cells and network architectures. *Neural Computation* 31, 7 (2019), 1235–1270.
- [69] Zhou Yu, Xingyu Shi, and Zhaoning Zhang. 2023. A multi-head self-attention transformer-based model for traffic situation prediction in terminal areas. *IEEE Access* 11 (2023), 16156–16165.
- [70] Jie Zeng and Jinjun Tang. 2022. Modeling dynamic traffic flow as visibility graphs: A network-scale prediction framework for lane-level traffic flow based on LPR data. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 24, 4 (2022), 4173–4188. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2022.3231959>

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